

METAL ORGANIC FRAMEWORKS-INTEGRATED SEPARATORS FOR INTERNAL GAS ABSORPTION IN LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES

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Nowadays, lithium ion batteries (LIBs) are respected as the most promising and essential energy storage systems in electrification of transportation, portable electronics, etc. [1]. Currently recognized cathode and anode materials are layered lithium transition metal oxides (TMOs) such as $\text{Li}_{1-x}(\text{Ni}_{1-y-z}\text{Mn}_y\text{Co}_z)_{1-x}\text{O}_2$ (NMC) and graphite, respectively. Among the various strategies to increase the specific capacity (≥ 200 mAh/g) and cycle life (> 1200 cycles) over a wide voltage range, increasing the fraction of highly redox-active Ni in NMC cathode materials (Ni-rich NMC) appears to be very effective. However, operation of NMC cathode LIBs in liquid electrolyte results in the evolution of several gases; mainly being H_2 , O_2 , CO , CO_2 and RH , which pose problems causing battery performance loss, volume expansion, degradation and safety issues [2]. The particular gas evolution causes are electrochemical oxidation of organic electrolyte, electrochemical decomposition of residual Li_2CO_3 species formed on the surface of Ni-rich NMC cathodes and structural instability of NMC cathode at high states of charge (SOC) [3].

In the EU-funded project PHOENIX (grant agreement No. 101103702), with the purpose of scavenge of the above-mentioned gases, the aim is to design and develop various metal organic frameworks (MOFs) integrated separators to be integrated in LIBs to minimize significant volume changes and electrode degradation during long cycles [4]. MOFs composed of metal ions and organic ligands are considered as idealized materials for gas absorption and storage in LIB due to their highly ordered pore structure and tunable size. This work describes, the initial developments on the nanosized zirconium (Zr) metal organic frameworks (Zr-MOFs-808) which are synthesized by using the easy and scalable solvothermal method. The synthesized Zr-MOFs-808 has been intensively characterized by XRD, SEM (Figure 1), EDAX etc. for their further optimization. Finally, Zr-MOFs-808-integrated poly (vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-HFP) thin film solid polymer separators (Figure 1) have been fabricated for efficient hydrogen (H_2) storage application in LIBs.

Figure 1. SEM image of Zr-MOFs-808 nanoparticle and Zr-MOFs-808-integrated thin film polymer separator.

REFERENCES

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